

The impact of relief on land use in Karabakh

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Abstract: Relief plays an important role in the formation of the environment as a factor affecting the climate, natural vegetation, soils, as well as human settlement and economic activity in various parts of the Earth's surface. Carrying out reconstruction work, establishing economic areas, and restoring settlement in our lands liberated from occupation are one of the main goals of our Republic. In this regard, it is very important to study the relief of Karabakh, which is the study area, as an environmental factor. The article examines the height amplitude of the Karabakh relief, the impact of endodynamic and exodynamic processes on the environment and land use. Thus, the relief of the study area is mainly mountainous, 38.4 percent of which is above 1000 m. This is also unfavorable for the establishment of arable land and the placement of large farms. However, there are such residential areas in highlands and there are favorable conditions for homestead farming. Highlands are also used as pastures. 43.8 percent of the area is up to 500 m and is quite suitable for the construction of infrastructure and agricultural areas.

Keywords: relief, land use and land cover, hypsometry, endodynamic processes, exodynamic processes

Introduction. The ecological role of relief depends on the overall relief structure, elevation, steepness, slope length, and slope aspect. Relief is an important environmental factor, influencing climate, soils, vegetation, and wildlife. This is manifested through changes in other abiotic factors, creating diverse conditions for various species.

As we know, relief is an orographic factor and is closely related to abiotic factors. The abiotic factor of nature is understood as the inanimate components of the environment. This also includes climate, soil, geological and hydrological conditions. Relief, as a component of this factor, plays an important role in the formation of the environment [2, 4]. The main orographic factor in the formation of the environment and land use is considered to be altitude. In connection with altitude, the average temperature decreases, daily temperature differences increase, precipitation, wind speed and radiation intensity increase, atmospheric pressure and gas concentration decrease. Depending on the size of the forms, the relief is divided into several parts: Macrorelief - mountains, intermountain depressions, lowlands; mesorelief - hills, ridges, ravines, etc.; microrelief - small depressions, hollows, cirques, ridges, etc. All this affects plants and animals, and as a result, vertical zonation occurs. Mountain ranges act primarily as climatic barriers, as moist air cools as it rises over the mountains, causing heavy rainfall on the windward slopes. All of this, in turn, affects land use and population settlement.

In addition to climate, relief can affect and change the hydrological regime of water systems, including rivers and lakes. High slopes and deep valleys create conditions for the formation of waterfalls and create fast currents. At the same time, slow currents and more stagnant waters form on flat plains and smooth surfaces. These differences in hydrological regime play an important role in the formation of living conditions and resource richness of ecosystems.

Relief can also create microecological conditions that support different species and ecosystems [4]. For example, cliffs and steep slopes can serve as shelters for many plant and animal species. Mountain slopes are also covered with different types of forests depending on altitude and exposure.

Land use and land cover (LULC) represents the interaction of people and the Earth's surface, which plays an important role in meeting the immediate needs of people [1, 5]. LULC covers a wide area from natural surfaces to agricultural lands or built-up areas. It not only provides food, industrial/residential space that is important for people, but also leads to an increase in the concentration of climate change [6]. The increase in the world population, the rapid growth and expansion of settlements lead to a shortage of areas suitable for land use. In this regard, the topic of the article is considered very relevant.

Analysis and discussion. The studied area is located on the southeastern slope of the Lesser Caucasus within the borders of Azerbaijan. Its area is 16054.26 km². In the relief of Karabakh, endogenous and exogenous processes have developed in a mutual manner, forming various forms. In particular, morphostructures related to endogenous processes predominate in their formation.

The Lesser Caucasus has very complex relief conditions, and ancient mountains, volcanic plateaus, and foothill plains replace each other here. The orographic elements that form the main morphostructural units for the studied area are the Lesser Caucasus Mountains and the Karabakh volcanic plateau, within which small morphostructural and morphosculptural units are located. The main morphostructural units include the Murovdag Range, the Karabakh Range, the Mikhtoken Range, the Eastern Goycha Range, the Karabakh Plain, and the Arazyani Plain. In general, Karabakh has a medium-mountainous relief in terms of altitude. The Lesser Caucasus, located in the southwest of the Republic of Azerbaijan, differs from the relief of other territories due to its unique characteristics.

Depending on the hypsometric level and vertical differentiation, morphostructures with different characteristics are distributed from lowland to highland. The following mountainous belts can be distinguished in Karabakh according to the height differentiation of the morphostructural base, which acts as a geomorphological unit that complicates the relief and is formed by the activity of endogenous processes. The separation of height belts according to the relief helps to clearly select and independently study the forms of manifestation of the activity of both endodynamic and exodynamic processes, both separately and in mutual interaction. Before the relief, the main factor that forms the physical and geographical conditions is taken (vertical zonality).

The elevation zones of the study area were drawn in ArcMap 10.8 software based on the digital elevation model (ASTER DEM) of Karabakh. The height of the relief is clearly reflected in the hypsometric map of Karabakh (Figure). Despite the fact that Karabakh is considered mountainous according to its relief, the lowland area (-8-1000 m) covers a large part of Karabakh. The parts of Karabakh close to the border with Armenia - the northern, north-western part - are considered to be highland zones (above 2000 m) according to the hypsometric level.

The main exodynamic process shaping the relief in the lowland zone of the study area is the erosion and accumulative activity of rivers. Here, depending on the intensive activity of the rivers, the ravine-gobu network is also quite dense, which directly affects the spread of badlands. The activity of endodynamic processes in the lowland area is manifested by seismic events. Although the manifestation of these events in the relief has been formed over many years, tectonic movements in the middle mountain belt are still occurring in the present period. As a result of endodynamic processes, faults occur in the watershed mountains and antecedent valleys are formed. Transverse faults occur along the lines cut by the Khachinchay, Tartarchay and Gargarchay rivers.

In the middle mountainous belt, the erosion and accumulative activity of rivers is mainly dominant. Landslides are observed less here than in the Greater Caucasus. Landslides occur mainly in places where unstable, well-permeable rocks prevail, crossed by the Tartarchay and Hakarichay rivers. The intensity of landslide processes decreases on the southwestern slope. From gravitational processes, avalanche and erosion processes are observed on the slopes of the Boyuk Kirs (2725 m), Girkhgyz (2830 m), and Ziyaret (2480 m) mountains. Avalanche and erosion materials have been collected here.

Although exaration processes are rarely observed in the studied area, they are observed on peaks higher than 3000 m, depending on the altitude. As a result of exaration processes, unique relief forms such as karsts and trough valleys have been formed here. Due to the high observation of the quantities of morphometric indicators of the relief in the high-mountainous belt (vertical fragmentation and inclination indicators are high, and horizontal fragmentation is relatively weak), the intensity of exogenous processes further increases ecogeomorphological stress. Depending on the high-mountainousness, the accumulation process is intensive and the corresponding relief forms are formed. The erosion activity of rivers also acts as an environmental factor that forms the fragmented conditions of the relief [3].

Fig. Amplitude of Karabakh's relief

Based on the compiled hypsometric map of the studied area, it can be noted that the total area covered by the lowland area (-8-1000 m) is 9890.31 km², which covers 61.60% of the total area. The area of the mid-mountain area (1000 - 2000 m) is 3932.86 km², and the area of the highland area (2000-3588 m) is 2231.09 km² (Table).

In the highland belt, exodynamic processes such as slope processes, gravitational processes, landslides (water-mud), avalanches, area erosion, nival and glacial processes, deluvial processes, solifluction, floods, etc. predominate, which negatively affects the use of the area. Thus, the highlands cover only 13.9% of Karabakh, which are used for summer pastures, as well as for tourism. The high mountain belt, steep cliffs, and sharply dissected relief are considered very favorable for lovers of sports tourism.

Table 1. Distribution quantities of the amplitude of the Karabakh relief over the territory

Relief height (m)	Area	
	km ²	%
-8-500	7031,81	43,8
500-1000	2858,5	17,8
1000-1500	2046,85	12,8
1500-2000	1886,01	11,7
2000-2500	1160,88	7,2
2500-3000	699,79	4,4
3000-3588	370,42	2,3

Since the uplift processes occurring in the modern period for the middle mountain belt (1000-2000 m) are mainly manifested in a weak and mild differential form, this is clearly noticeable in the

height of the ridges and ridges. In this zone, residential areas, roads, and farm areas have been built in areas with low inclination. In the future, it is planned to carry out work in this direction in the vacant areas within this belt.

In the low mountain belt, morphostructures such as the Front Caucasus Sloping Plain, the Karabakh Plain, the Haremi, Inje, Gayan, and Yazy Plains are located. Despite the fact that the low mountain zone occupies 61.60% or 9890.31 km² of the total Karabakh territory, it does not hold a key position in the selection of the Karabakh relief due to the complexity of its relief. Within this belt, there are very favorable conditions for the construction of farm areas and infrastructure, the placement of agricultural lands and residential areas. It is currently the zone with the largest population, and will be increasingly mastered by resettled families in the future.

In the future, due to the increased settlement of the population in the studied area, the relief will be mastered even more intensively, which, in turn, will lead to some changes. As we know, the transformation of natural landscapes is not entirely related to anthropogenic activity. Since ancient times, at the end of human economic activity, derivative landscapes have formed in place of the original landscapes, and these landscapes were selected for their natural recovery properties. There is almost no area of landscapes that are not subject to anthropogenic impact on the Earth's surface, as well as in the study area. Most of the transformed landscapes, no matter how much they have changed, retain a number of structural elements of the natural landscape. However, with the increase in anthropogenic loads, horizontal and vertical differentiation (zonality, azonality patterns) is also violated. Unlike natural landscapes, in anthropogenic landscapes, such features as soil-vegetation cover, biological and biochemical cycles, water and heat balance, etc. are also subject to significant changes. The role of modern technology and the level of socio-economic development in the emergence of all these signs is great. In recent times, along with the problem of desertification spreading both in the world and in our country, large-scale irrigation and land reclamation measures are also changing the landscapes more. This has caused the landscapes to change by spreading more widely in the area between the Terterchay and Gargarchay rivers in the studied area. As we know, the share of anthropogenic landscapes decreases from the plains to the highlands. Thus, in Karabakh, anthropogenic landscapes in the plains include areas dominated by shifting cultivation, artificial forests, agro-irrigation landscapes, pastures, mining, urban and recreational landscapes.

In the wide valleys of the Tartar and Gargar rivers, in the confluences of the rivers, forests and shrubs have been replaced by agro-landscapes and seliteb complexes. This zone is dominated by a temperate-hot semi-desert dry-steppe climate with dry summers and a temperate-hot semi-desert dry-steppe climate with dry winters. The natural landscapes of the irrigated areas have been drastically fragmented and fundamentally changed by the use of canals, collectors and other facilities. In areas where irrigation agriculture prevails, natural landscapes have remained in very small areas. Irrigation in these areas has given rise to the formation of modern anthropogenic landscapes, agro-irrigation landscapes, which the arid climate has made necessary. The implementation of perennial irrigation has also led to the creation of micro-technogenic relief forms. Agro-irrigation landscapes are widespread not only in flat areas, but also in low mountainous areas with arid, fragmented relief.

In general, it can be noted that the most intensively used soils suitable for agriculture are brown mountain-forest, brown mountain-forest, mountain-black and mountain gray-brown (chestnut) soils. Each of these soils is the main soil type of Karabakh and is spread over large areas. At the same time, pastures, which are an important feed base for livestock, are also found in mountain-meadow soils. An increase in the intensity of erosion and weathering processes is observed in high-mountainous zones, which complicates farming in these zones. Another reason is related to the occurrence of natural disasters - floods. A number of measures must be taken to make such soils suitable for agriculture. It is inevitable to take measures such as protecting forests, building flood protection facilities to regulate the flow, afforesting slopes, creating terraces, efficiently using pasture areas, preparing and using organic and mineral fertilizers to increase the productivity and fertility of soils, etc.

Result. The main exodynamic process shaping the relief in the lowland belt (61.60% of the total area) is the erosion and accumulative activity of the relief rivers. Here, depending on the intensive activity of the rivers, the ravine-gobu network is also quite dense, which directly affects the spread of badlands. The activity of endodynamic processes in the lowland area is manifested by seismic events. However, these events do not prevent the development of the territory and land use. Thus, this area has been developed more by the population and this process continues.

In the middle mountain belt (24.5% of the total area), tectonic movements are still occurring in the present period. Faults occur in the watershed mountains, antecedent valleys are formed. Although

volcanism is relatively weak in this belt, its traces are found here. However, this zone is suitable for the construction of roads, residential areas and homestead farms.

The high-mountain belt (13.9% of the total area) is distinguished by its high ecogeomorphological tension due to the high quantities of relief morphometric indicators (relatively weak horizontal fragmentation). Plateaus formed from lava covers have formed on the Karabakh volcanic plateau under the influence of volcanism. Depending on the high-mountainity, accumulation and exfoliation processes are intensively active and corresponding relief forms are formed. These processes, which are more pronounced in the areas surrounding Boyuk Ishigly and Gyzylbogaz, have spread to karsts, circuses, and trough valleys. The erosion activity of rivers also acts as an environmental factor that shapes the fragmented conditions of the relief. This area is mainly used as summer pastures. It also has very favorable conditions for sports tourism enthusiasts with its steep cliffs and sharply fragmented relief.

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